

Efficient Method of Road Anomaly Recognition Using Deep Learning Coupled with Data Augmentation Approach

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Abstract

In recent years, Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras have played a vital role in the surveillance of public and private areas. The primary objective of surveillance cameras is to monitor human behavior and road situations. In the real-world situation, detecting, and recognizing abnormal activities poses significant challenges due to the densely crowded environment and the composite nature of transportation systems. These factors make it problematic to automatically identify anomalies that occur while traveling leading to emergencies and threatening human life and property. In response to these challenges, Road Anomaly Recognition Surveillance Systems (RARSS) have been deployed to monitor and detect abnormalities on streets, highways, and roads. This research specifically investigated conventional and human-centered road anomalies encompassing snatching, accidents, fighting, and car fires. The proposed Real-time Road Anomaly Recognition system is formulated as a classification task, involving the analysis and processing of real-time CCTV videos. The proposed study investigated the deep learning model of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) coupled with the Data Augmentation (DA) approach to address the frame flickering problem in real-time videos. Furthermore, we introduced a benchmark real-world Road Anomaly/Outlier Dataset (ROD) containing roads, streets, and highways videos and images with different illumination situations that presented various road anomalies. Experimentation using different pre-trained CNN models i.e., VGG19, InceptionV3, ResNet50, MobileNetV2, and DenseNet201 coupled with a DA approach has been performed on the ROD dataset. The experimental results demonstrated that the InceptionV3 model performed best with the augmentation approach compared to other deep learning models. It achieved the best accuracy of 98.80% in recognizing road anomalies.

Index Terms: Closed-Circuit Television, Convolutional Neural Network, Data Augmentation, Road Outlier Recognition, Transfer Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Anything that deviates from the usual or the standard is considered an Anomaly. In real-world applications, road anomaly recognition seeks to identify instances that differ significantly from all other normal instances on the roads. The surveillance system aims to recognize normal and abnormal activities to ensure people's protection and road safety management. The usage of Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras is the most widespread method for real-time security and surveillance. Many CCTV cameras have been installed for security reasons in various municipal and private sectors during the past years. These CCTV cameras can be useful in spotting irregularities and responding appropriately when something is out of the ordinary [1]. The capacity to identify abnormalities in actual settings is made possible by surveillance cameras. While automatically identifying aberrant sights may be difficult, it is easy to identify typical scenes in real-world scenarios. Acquiring and utilizing

large amounts of labeled data presents a significant problem in the training of models: anomaly identification. Due to time constraints and the expensive (especially unusual) procedure of categorizing the dataset, data collecting takes a long time. Imbalanced datasets with a ratio of anomaly cases to usual road images that is far higher than this issue. To enhance the precision and stability of automated road anomaly detection systems and ultimately contribute to more efficient and safe road infrastructure, these obstacles must be overcome using various strategies, including data augmentation, economical labeling, and domain adaptation [2]. Several approaches have been proposed to overcome these problems with autonomous road anomaly detection. One method that uses video cameras to automatically identify anomalies on the road is the Video Traffic Surveillance System (VTSS) [3]. The VTSS divides traffic motion into "accident" and "no accident" categories while reducing human involvement in traffic data collection and monitoring. However, the absence of spatial intelligence, and poor lighting impact bed performance, and the

inability to identify irregularities on the road [4]. This research is absorbed in the development of a scene-invariant real-time road Anomaly recognition framework using deep learning. In the first place, a unified novel Road Anomaly Dataset (ROD) dataset comprising four distinct and critical road anomalies namely accidents, car fire, fighting, and snatching (gunpoint) has been acquired via CCTV cameras in different illumination conditions such as low streetlight or nighttime, and varying camera distances that can affect the quality of captured videos. Data Augmentation (DA) is applied to the collected data to avoid the model overfitting problem [5]. We have formulated the road Anomaly recognition problem as a classification task. Different variants of the pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network CNN model like VGG19, InceptionV3, ResNet50, MobileNetv2, and DenseNet201 are investigated to choose the most accurate model for the real-time road Anomaly recognition framework.

The main contributions of this research are:

- We proposed the improvement in the road surveillance system integrated with our proposed RARSS to automatically detect various types of road anomalies in video feeds in limited visibility, perspective, and scale change.
- We proposed a novel technique for classifying road anomalies such as road accidents, car fire, fighting, and snatching (gunpoint) in videos using the pre-trained CNN models integrated with the data augmentation approach.
- We utilized transfer-learning strategies are used to increase the strength, potential, and generalization of the model.
- The development of a unified novel ROD dataset having 2487 images and 20 videos captured through CCTV cameras from different locations of roads, streets, and internet resources.
- The experimental results demonstrated that the deep learning model of InceptionV3 coupled with the Data Augmentation (DA) approach achieved the best accuracy 98.80% as compared with other deep learning models.

II. RELATED WORK

Recognizing road anomalies involving typical abnormalities in in-vehicle scene entities is a crucial aspect of traffic behavior modeling [6]. The availability of traffic video scenes has led to enhanced efforts in video analytics and road Anomaly recognition. While computer vision models often analyze all-purpose traffic scenes to distinguish abnormal from normal events, methods like the Markov model [7], and [8]; Markov Random Field [9], and [10]; and Sparse Reconstruction have shown some success. However, the initiation of deep learning has brought significant advancements in road Anomaly recognition, leading to a predominant use of deep neural networks in recent studies [11]. For instance, Bortnikov et al. [12] critically evaluated existing techniques for the automatic recognition of accident scenes and discussed the inherent complexities associated with road safety within smart

cities. They proposed an advanced accident recognition model using a pre-trained 3D CNN. Their model was trained on traffic videos extracted from gaming contexts and employed dual testing functions—one incorporating visual movement and another without. While their model accurately identifies traffic incidents in real-world recordings, it exhibits limitations in effectively detecting accidents occurring during nighttime or under poor lighting conditions. Kim et al. [13] reported a new method for detecting traffic accidents that combined a pre-activated ResNet and a spatiotemporal 3D-CNN with a feature pyramid network regional architecture. Their proposed solution took advantage of the period input methodology to reduce the computing difficulty while maintaining high detection accuracy. Experimental results show that the proposed model performs better in accuracy and recall metrics than the state-of-the-art. This approach's sensitivity to the quality of the input data, which might lead to worse functioning in bad weather or in low light, needlessly restricts its efficacy. The Suspicious Activity Detection (SAD) system developed by Selvi et al. [14] is based on an Enhanced Convolutional Neural Network (ECNN). The purpose of the study was to ascertain how successfully surveillance video recordings identified suspicious behavior, such as robbery and execution. Accuracy, precision, false positive, and false negative rates were among the assessment measures. According to the trial findings, the average precision and accuracy for identifying suspicious activity were 97.05% and 96.74%, respectively. However, it is significant to note that the suggested approach may not be appropriate for various lighting scenarios. Phyo et al. [15] conducted a study on Human Action Recognition (HAR) using two human activity datasets. They formulated human action recognition as a skeletal-joint motion to monitor the elderly, suspicious individuals, and hazardous items in public places with the support of deep learning algorithms and image pre-processing. However, the limited motion sets make it less efficient. There have been quite a few contributions made by researchers using real-time activity recognition deep learning models like YOLO. For example, Tian et al. [16] introduced an automatic car accident detection method leveraging the Cooperative Vehicle Infrastructure System (CVIS) and established a novel image dataset named CAD-CVIS. They incorporated Multi-Scale Feature Fusion (MSFF) and a loss function with dynamic weights to improve the detection performance of small substances. However, the limitation of this approach is communication overhead due to the real-time scene capture via roadside cameras and its transmission to remote servers. Ullah et al. [17] introduced a computationally intelligent Violence Detection (VD) method. Initially, the video captured by a visual sensor undergoes processing using a lightweight Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). Subsequently, temporal optical flow features are extracted from the informative videos. Finally, a final feature map is generated by integrating a Multi-Layer Long and Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network to determine violence patterns within the frame sequences. While the consequences demonstrate some improvement in method accuracy, it is noteworthy that the accuracy achieved in outdoor monitoring remains at 49%.

Pillai et al. [18] conducted a study on real-time image improvement for automatic accident detection using CCTV with deep learning. The proposed system adopted Mini-YOLO for detection, Deep SORT for tracking, and a Support Vector Machine (SVM) for classification. The Mini-YOLO model operated at a rate of 28 frames per second, achieving an average precision AP score of 34.2. Additionally, the SVM, employing the radial basis function kernel, demonstrated impressive results with 96% accuracy, 94% recall, and 96% AUC during the classification stage. The limitation of this approach is that relies on a static definition of accidents, primarily focusing on damaged vehicles. Faster Region-based Convolutional Neural Network (Faster R-CNN) is another computer vision-based object recognition technique that is also used for automatic road Anomaly recognition particularly snatching scenes that involve the criminal having a gun or knife in hand. By including a Region Proposal Network (RPN), it improves the efficiency and precision of region-based convolutional neural networks. To identify objects, the RPN effectively produces region suggestions. FRCNN is frequently used for accurate and quick object recognition in video frames. In this regard, Carrobbles et al. [19] and Berardini et al. [20] have developed an FRCNN model for the automatic recognition of knives and handguns in surveillance videos. The dataset used included gun images from the publicly available Weapon detection dataset providing valuable data on criminal activities on the road [21]. Similarly, Hnoohom et al. [22] introduced an FRCNN-based approach for the automatic recognition of anomalies such as weapons. However, a notable flaw in their model is the limited dataset for knife and pistol weapon images, which was collected exclusively during daytime and under bright illumination conditions. Therefore, the detection of weapon images may yield inaccurate results in low illumination conditions. Furthermore, the discussion on the real-world applicability and potential challenges of implementing the proposed system is notably limited. One significant challenge in deep learning-based automatic road Anomaly recognition is the limited availability of training data. To address this, data augmentation must be incorporated as an effective fine-tuning technique for enhancing model performance. Krizhevsky et al. [23] demonstrated the effectiveness of data augmentation on the ImageNet dataset for efficient image classification that may be applied in road Anomaly recognition tasks when formulated as a classification problem. Various data augmentation strategies, discussed in the literature fall into two main categories [24]. The first category involves conventional transformations, incorporating color modifications with an affine image transformation. The second category, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) employs the min-max approach to generate new images without supervision [25]. After an extensive review of the relevant literature and to the best of our knowledge, previous works in automatic road Anomaly recognition have primarily focused on specific aspects such as road accidents, traffic monitoring, activity recognition, and weapon detection. However, there exists a notable gap in the literature, as no single work provides a unified platform for the automatic recognition of other critical road anomalies, such as car fires, fights,

and snatching incidents. This research identifies and addresses this gap by introducing a novel real-time road Anomaly recognition framework using deep learning. Our framework leverages the development of a novel unified Road Anomaly Dataset (ROD) comprising four distinct anomalies i.e., road accidents, car fires, fighting, and snatching scenes. The ROD consists of real-time CCTV video footage and images, enhanced with data augmentation techniques to expand model performance, generalization, and robustness. This approach addresses the challenges associated with limited training data and variations in real-world scenarios. Additionally, we employed five different variants of CNN namely VGG19, InceptionV3, ResNet50, DenseNet201, and MobileNetV2 to determine the most effective model for automatic road Anomaly recognition.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Our proposed study is a real-time Road Anomaly Recognition framework using deep learning coupled with a data augmentation approach as illustrated in figure I. The benchmark of our proposed study is the data collection which is named the ROD dataset that contains four road anomalies such as road accidents, car fire, fighting, and snatching scenes. The data was collected using real-time CCTV traffic surveillance videos and then frames were extracted. Data augmentation is adopted to enhance the dataset to decrease the overfitting problems. In the next step, five different variants of CNN are applied to the dataset and evaluated using performance assessment metrics such as Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F-1 Score.

Figure I: Proposed Study of Road Outlier Recognition Framework

A. Road Anomaly Dataset or ROD

The lack of a unified publicly available dataset for several road anomalies poses a significant challenge in real-time road anomaly recognition. Consequently, we undertook the task of creating a novel dataset by gathering information from diverse city locations using CCTV cameras, considering various road abnormalities. The result of this work is the Road Anomaly Dataset (ROD), which is made up of several extracted frames for roads, streets, and highways from surveillance recordings. We standardized the duration of each video to 10 seconds and captured video footage at a frame rate of 30 frames per second (fps) to produce a high-quality dataset. The goal of

this method was to extract more relevant frames from every video. The necessary anomaly scenes were extracted from road footage using the Python OpenCV program and then converted into frames for additional analysis.

The general statistics of the recently generated ROD dataset are shown in table I. We concentrated on acts that were essentially associated with violence, threatened human life, or presented potential risks to property while selecting the ROD dataset. We specifically noted abnormal scenes of accidents, car fire, fighting, and snatching (gunpoint).

As shown in figure II, the ROD dataset is divided into four different categories, and an assigned number between 0 and 3 is given to each category 0 represents accidents, 1 vehicle fire, 2 fights, and 3 snatchings (at gunpoint).

Table I: Road Anomaly Dataset (ROD) Description

Road Outlier	No. of Images	No. of Videos
Accident	696	5
Car Fire	385	6
Fighting	729	4
Snatching	677	5
Total	2487	20

Figure II: ROD Dataset (a) Accident (b) Car Fire (c) Fighting (d) Snatching(Gunpoint)

B. Data Pre-processing

To automatically identify road anomalies pre-processing the image dataset is essential before supplying it to the deep learning model. It helps to remove noise and extraneous data from the model, which shortens training timeframes, increases model accuracy, and boosts overall effectiveness. To comply with the OpenCV library convert the images from color to gray and then adopt the Keras library for applying more processing. Every image is downsized to 224×224 image size with the original aspect ratio of each image being ignored. The last step in the pre-processing process is mean subtraction, which involves calculating the average of all the image's pixel values and subtracting it from each pixel. The purpose of this phase is to ensure that the picture is standardized and aligned with factors such as weights and biases.

Subsequently, data augmentation techniques are applied to the dataset after preprocessing to make our framework scene invariant.

C. Data Augmentation (DA)

Data Augmentation (DA) is a machine learning method that is used to enlarge a training dataset by applying transformation techniques to an existing dataset [26] without any modification of the dataset. The primary object is to create additional instances that represent variations of the original data, thereby enlarging the dataset without the need for new real-world data collection. Typically applied in computer vision tasks, DA generates images with different transformations. These transformations generate new representations of data variations and enhance the comprehension of the dataset. Additionally, DA also helps prevent model overfitting and increases its resilience to variations in input data [27]. In our case, we adjusted the ROD dataset by applying the flipping, rotating, and translation techniques as seen in the images in figure III.

Figure III: ROD Dataset with Augmentation Approach (a) Accident (b) Car Fire (c) Fighting (d) Snatching

D. Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

After the literature study, we observed that CNN is one of the most frequently used deep learning models for image identification and classification. Figure IV illustrates the CNN architectural diagram. A typical CNN architecture comprises an input layer, convolutional layers, pooling layers, fully connected layers, and an output layer [28]. The activation function and the dropout layer are two additional essential parameters that are in addition to these layers. The digital input image is made up of a matrix of pixels that is fed to the CNN model. Image dimensions are expressed as $h \times w \times d$. Where; h stands for height, w for width, and d for the total number of metrics used to indicate an image dimension.

The convolutional layer in the CNN model is used to get information from the input images. This layer receives a small rectangle of input data, which is equal to the filter size (f) or kernel size.

The user selects certain areas of the image matrix by using the kernel size, which is determined by equations i.e., eq. (1), eq. (2), and eq. (3).

$$\text{Image Matrix} = h * w * d \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Parensfilter} = f(h) * f(w) * f(d) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Output} (h - f(h) - 1) * (w - f(w) - 1) * 1 \quad (3)$$

Figure IV: CNN-based Road Anomaly Recognition

Subsequently, a new matrix, known as a feature map of the image, is then constructed capturing the image point of interest. The eq. (4), shows the formula for computing a single output matrix.

$$A_j = f\left(\sum_{i=1}^N I_i * K_{i,j} + B_j\right) \quad (4)$$

Where; I represent the input vector, and K is the corresponding kernel size, and B_j is the bias parameter. ReLU (Rectifier Linear Unit), which functions as an activation function and is a component of the convolutional layer, gives the CNN model non-linearity and the ability to operate on positive values of image pixels.

$$f(x) = \max(0, x) \text{ (ReLU)} \quad (5)$$

The pooling layer is the third layer in CNN. This layer's primary purpose is to reduce the input image's size while retaining its key characteristics. The pooling layer has two parameters, i.e., the Filter, which is a tiny matrix, and the Stride, which is the number of steps to transfer a filter across the whole picture after computation while preserving the relevant data. Images are multi-classified using the Softmax activation function, while binary classification uses the Sigmoid activation function.

E. Transfer Learning Approach

In the deep learning paradigm, a substantial amount of training data, time, and computer resources are required for conventional CNNs. On the other hand, using a transfer learning approach in conjunction with pre-trained deep neural networks provides a quicker and more affordable solution for classification problems. In this work, we used the transfer learning approach for the real-time road Anomaly recognition task. The pre-existing classifiers i.e., VGG19, InceptionV3, ResNet50, DenseNet201, and MobileNetV2, are used in this work.

F. Visual Geometry Group-19 (VGG19)

VGG19 is a pre-trained CNN model with 19 layers out of which 16 are convolutional layers and 3 are fully connected

layers [28]. It is capable of categorizing photos into 1000 different item groups. The ImageNet database, which has one million photos arranged into 1000 categories, trains VGG19. Considering that every convolutional layer employs numerous 3×3 filters, this automatic image categorization technique is quite popular.

G. Inception V3

The Inception-V3 architecture makes use of 'Inception Modules' [29], which are collections of pooling procedures, dimensionality reductions, and parallel convolutional layers with different sizes (1×1 , 3×3 , and 5×5). These modules make it easier to extract features inside a single layer at various sizes and levels of complexity. Factorization approaches are utilized by Inception-V3 to minimize computing demands while preserving representational strength [30]. To efficiently reduce computational complexity while maintaining the network capacity to capture significant characteristics, it breaks down bigger convolutions, such as a 5×5 convolution into two sequential 3×3 convolutions.

H. ResNet 50 Model

The CNN-based ResNet-50 model has 50 layers and excels in extracting fine-grained image data for more precise representations. Its primary innovation is the inclusion of residual blocks with shortcut connections also referred to as skip connections that enable improved gradient mobility [31], and [32]. This innovation solves the vanishing gradient issue, which facilitates the training of deeper networks.

I. DenseNet201

A CNN-based model with 201 layers for detection and classification is called 'DenseNet-201' [33]. This architecture maximizes feature reuse and reduces duplication by allowing each layer to accept input from all levels that came before it [34]. This architecture not only improves feature reuse across layers but also reduces the vanishing gradient problem that deep networks often encounter. Because of its compact internal representations,

DenseNet-201 is a helpful feature extractor for a diversity of computer vision applications.

J. MobileNetV2

MobileNetV2, a convolutional neural network architecture, was developed especially for low-resource settings and portable applications [35]. It makes use of an inverse residual structure, with the bottleneck layer attached to the residual structure. The major objectives of adopting MobileNetV2 are to minimize its size, reduce latency, improve performance speed, and reduce the number of parameters. This model has 153 layers and operates with an input layer size of 224x224x3.

K. Evaluation Metrics

Deep learning techniques are calculated with useful measures, such as Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-Score, which are used to measure the model performance and accuracy. To measure this model is well generalizing to other datasets. A basic statistic is called accuracy means the number of correct forecasts. The ratio between the true positive predictions to all positive predictions is used to measure the identification precision. Recall is a ratio of all real positive predictions to demonstrate how a model can accurately identify all pertinent occurrences. To measure the F1-score, a trustworthy measure that provides a detailed assessment of a model's performance, recall, and accuracy are shared harmonically.

Equations (6–9) are presented as a model score:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FP+TN+FN} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{F1 - Score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (9)$$

IV. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

This section gives a summary of our methodology for identifying road anomalies in several real-world videos along with the experimental setup with their implementation. There are several Python libraries available such as Pandas, NumPy, TensorFlow, and Keras are used for investigating our model. Our proposed model is being trained in the Python 3 environment using a streamlet environment. We conducted thorough testing on a system that has an 8 GB GPU and an Intel Core i7 CPU to calculate the performance of our suggested framework.

A. Implementation

The CNN model operates the Keras API and is composed of two parts: the head model and the base model. Pre-trained ImageNet weights were used to prime the basic model, which used ImageNet class labels to categorize input frames. The CNN model performs well in tasks related to image classification and recognition. To match the proportions of the original training frames, the input shape

was adjusted to 244x244x3. Using the output of the base model as an input, the head model was built. This required the addition of a 2D average pooling layer with predetermined x and y pool sizes. The output of this layer was flattened and fed to the fully connected layer comprising 512 nodes ReLU as an activation function. The class categories corresponded to the sizes of the output layer, which used Softmax classification.

B. Hyperparameter Tuning

We optimized our model using hyperparameter tuning. Hyperparameters are set values that control the training process, as opposed to model parameters, which are discovered through data analysis. The learning rate, capacity, and generalization ability of the network are all impacted by these choices [36]. A few important hyperparameters include the learning rate, architecture (number of layers and neurons), activation functions, batch size, epochs, regularization strategies, weight initialization, and optimizer choice. The process of hyperparameter tuning entails trial and error and iterative modifications to determine the ideal configuration for a given job, which is frequently necessary to achieve optimal model performance. Adaptive Moment Estimation (Adam) [37] is utilized in the performance on a validation set reaches a plateau thus preventing overfitting. In addition to saving training time training phase of our deep learning model for real-time road anomaly recognition. The Adam optimizer combines concepts from both RMSprop and momentum optimization, aiming to adjust learning rates adaptively for each parameter. The adaptation process involves considering both the historical average of gradients and their recent magnitudes. This dual consideration facilitates swifter convergence and enhances the algorithm's ability to effectively handle sparse gradients within deep learning models [38]. We included the Adam optimizer with a learning rate (lr) of 0.0001, and batch size of 32 for the training model and used "sparse_categorical_crossentropy" as the training loss function since it works best with our classes, and then fit the generator function to train the model using early stopping technique. We utilize the early stopping technique that stops the training process when the model and processing resources, this technique also enhances the model's ability to generalize fresh data. Early stopping helps to maintain the stability of the model, makes hyperparameter adjustment more effective, and makes it easier to choose the model that performs best on the validation set. The comparison of the training and validation accuracy learning curve for VGG19, InceptionV3, and ResNet50 are presented in figures, i.e., figure V, figure VI, and figure VII, respectively. The blue line is represented by training accuracy, while the orange lines depict validation accuracy. Figure VIII - figure X shows the relationship between validation and training loss for VGG19, InceptionV3, and ResNet50. Notably, InceptionV3 demonstrated the highest accuracy in both training and validation accuracy. The blue lines show training loss, whereas the orange lines represent validation loss. Loss serves as a measure penalizing incorrect predictions, indicating the model's inaccuracy in each epoch. Considerable is the InceptionV3 model with the proposed model achieved the lowest validation loss among the models analyzed.

Figure V: Training and Validation Accuracy of VGG19

Figure IX: Training and Validation Loss of Inception V3

Figure VI: Training and Validation Accuracy of InceptionV3

Figure X: Training and Validation Loss of ResNet50

Figure VII: Training and Validation Accuracy of ResNet50

Figure VIII: Training and Validation Loss of VGG19

C. Experimental Results

Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-Score are among the most widely utilized metrics for evaluating a model's performance and its generalization abilities across different datasets.

The comparison of diverse deep-learning models with proposed models for classifying road Anomaly images is represented in table II. We analyzed and evaluated that InceptionV3 with the proposed model achieved more accuracy as compared to the other algorithms.

The statistics of average classification results are shown in figures, i.e., figure XI - figure XIII, respectively.

Figure XI: VGG19 Test Results

Figure XII: ResNet50 Test Results

Figure XIII: InceptionV3 Test Results

Table II: Performance Evaluation of CNN Models on ROD Dataset with and without Data Augmentation

Model	CNN Model without Data Augmentation				CNN Model with Data Augmentation			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F-1 Score	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F-1 Score
VGG19	91.80	91.61	90.12	90.86	92.55	92.34	92.75	92.58
ResNet50	97.15	95.15	95.28	95.21	96.70	96.56	96.91	96.73
DenseNet201	94.20	94.12	94.30	94.21	97.50	97.52	97.67	97.59
MobileNetV2	96.30	96.60	96.71	96.65	98.50	98.48	98.60	98.54
Inception-V3	97.90	97.97	97.83	97.90	98.80	98.68	98.95	98.75

In machine learning, the confusion matrix is an essential tool for assessing a classification model's accuracy. In a multi-class classification issue, it decomposes the amounts of True Positives (TP), True Negatives (TN), False Positives (FP), and False Negatives (FN) for each class.

The confusion matrix delivers a detailed breakdown of the model's performance for each of the four classes: accidents, car fire, fight, and snatching, as depicted in figures, i.e., figure XIV – figure XVII.

Analyzing the confusion matrix reveals that the InceptionV3 model performs relatively well. We utilized our trained model to process the complete testing dataset, comprising 20 movies, processed one by one. Subsequently, we analyzed the outcomes to evaluate its performance on this unseen test data, which had not been confronted by the model before. The model was specifically engineered to exhibit the input video. Here are several screenshots showcasing different scenarios captured by the system. In the first scene, we sent a video with the filename ac001.mp4 showing a car accident. The model classified the frame as anomalous and gave it a "0 Accident" activity, as shown in figure XIV.

Figure XIV: Accident in Daylight

In the second scene, we watched a movie that appeared fighting in low light. Its filename was fg01.mp4. Figure XV illustrates the model identified the frame as abnormal and categorized it as "1 Fighting."

Figure XV: Fighting on the Street

In the third scene, we examined a video that showed a car fire on road parking in a day situation as seen in figure XVI, the model is detected as labeled "2 Fire," and the algorithm correctly categorized it as an Anomaly.

Figure XVI: Car Fire in Daylight

In the fourth scene a suspicious man holding a pistol in this scene. The frame was accurately recognized by the model as an Anomaly, and it was classified as "3 Snatching" as illustrated in figure XVII.

Figure XVII: Suspicious Person Shows a Gun for Snatching

V. DISCUSSION

Previous investigations have brought attention to the challenges associated with traffic accidents and street crimes, highlighting the necessity of artificial intelligence to improve monitoring in smart cities. A computer vision framework has been proposed to address these issues and increase the effectiveness of emergency responses to events. This multipurpose system uses parallel computing to provide an automatic alert system and deep learning models to detect irregularities on the road. A simple Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) method that handled each video frame individually in prior research encountered the "flickering label" problem when utilized for video categorization. The Road Anomaly Recognition Surveillance System (RORSS) that we have suggested looks at several road abnormalities, including automobile fires, fights, snatching, and accidents. The Real-time Road Anomaly Recognition system uses a rolling prediction strategy to solve the frame invariance problem and several CNN models with data augmentation to analyze real-time CCTV footage. Table III illustrates the higher performance of our model by comparing its accuracy with earlier research. This demonstrates how well our method works to improve accuracy and get over drawbacks found in earlier studies.

Table III: Accuracy Comparison with Previous Work

Year, Reference	Accuracy (%)
Tian et al, 2019 [16]	90.10
Selvi et al, 2022 [14]	98.04
Berardini et al, 2023 [20]	79.30
Proposed Model	98.80

VI. CONCLUSION

In this research, we proposed a model with a framework that integrates the pre-trained models of CNN coupled with the Data Augmentation (DA) technique in collaboration with a rolling prediction algorithm to improve the performance of the model and overcome the flickering problem during testing. Furthermore, we created a custom real-world Road Anomaly Dataset (ROD) of images and videos. The experiments are conducted using the ROD dataset with different CNN models such as VGG19, InceptionV3, ResNet50, MobileNetV2, and DenseNet201. Experimental results showed that the InceptionV3 model achieved the highest test accuracy at 98.80 surpassing the other models. The primary aim of this research is to help those people who are affected by incidents and overcome

staff involvement to monitor multiple traffic systems simultaneously. In the future researchers will work on fine-tuning our model to attain better mAP and the result shows the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve or ROC curve. A Segmentation approach will be applied to classify the road anomalies. Moreover, we will try to utilize our framework for other object detection applications such as vehicle classification.

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Authors Contributions

All the authors equally contributed to this study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest and confirm that this work is original and not plagiarized from any other source. The information obtained from all of the sources is properly recognized and cited below.

Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

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